

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

Deliverable reference number and title:

D8.3 – Highlights of the value-chain events

Due date of deliverable: 31/3/2021

Actual submission date: 30/9/21

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Type

R Document, report

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.

OTHER

Dissemination Level

PU Public

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 727698.

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On-line Value-chain events

Two on-line value chain events had been organised in collaboration with MAGIC project. The events had been organised on web due to COVID-19 crisis; the first took place on 17th of December 2020 and the second on 20th of January 2021.

1st on-line value chain event

The 1st online value chain event was supported by the EU projects BECOOL, BIKE, BFF, Biomagic, FORTE & GRACE (see agenda below). The event was focus on the lignocellulosic crops and the opportunities offering for the agricultural sector.

Value Chain Event on Lignocellulosic Crops
Opportunities for the agriculture sector

17th of December 2020

13:50	Get connected	
14:00	Welcome <i>Set the scene of the today workshop & presentation of PANACEA platform and MAGIC tools</i>	Dr. Efi Alexopoulou (CRES) Mr. Panayiotis Stamatelopoulos (AUA)
14:20	The BECOOL project on advanced lignocellulosic biofuels	Prof. Andrea Monti (UNIBO)
14:40	Biomass For Future - Towards competitive and sustainable lignocellulosic value chains	Dr. Herman Hofte (INRAE)
15:10	BIOmagic project – BIO products from lignocellulosic biomass	Prof. Mariusz Stolarski (UWM)
15:30	BIKE - Biofuels production at low ILUC risk for European sustainable bioeconomy	Prof. David Chiaramonti (RECORD)
15:50	Progress of demonstrating miscanthus and hemp based value chains in the GRACE project	Dr. Andreas Kiesel (UHOH)
16:10	Fiber crops for sustainable soil remediation and bio-based raw material production	Dr. Eleni G. Papazoglou (AUA)
16:30	Discussion on the value-chain of lignocellulosic crops	
17:15	End of the webinar	

Supported by the projects

The event was starting with a short introduction of the hosting projects (MAGIC & PANACEA). Then, the participants had the opportunity to be informed of the scope and

project of BECOOL project, where two kind of field trials are been carried out: a) perennial crops (like giant reed, miscanthus) on marginal lands in the Med region and b) annual herbaceous non-food crops (like biomass sorghum, sunn hemp) in rotation with food crops (wheat and corn). In this project the non-food crops are being tested as feedstock for advanced biofuels. BECOOL is a EU project on bioduels in collaboration with Brazil. Thereafter, two national reaserch projects had been presented and discussed: a) BFF project, a French project, testing selected lignocellulosic value chains in several sites in France and b) Biomagic in order biobased products to be developed from lignocellulosic biomass from feedstocks harvesting from marginal lands. Then, the event was continued with two EU funded projects; BIKE and Bio4A. BIKE is a project for low ILUC feedstock for advanced biofuels and Bio4A is project of biofuels, where camelina is being grown in rotation with cereals on dry lands in Spain, among other research activities. The event was closed with the presentation of FORTE project (Greece-China project), where bast fibre crops (hemp, flax and kenaf) are being growing on contaminated lands for decontamination and their feedstocks are being testing for bio-based production.

In the figure below presented some photos from this on-line value chain event.

Below is presented how the event had been disseminated through project website and social media.

17th of December 2020: Value Chain Event on Lignocellulosic Crops – Opportunities for the agriculture sector

14:00 H: WELCOME – SET THE SCENE OF THE TODAY WORKSHOP & PRESENTATION OF PANACEA PLATFORM AND MAGIC TOOLS
Dr. Efi Alexopoulos (CREG)

14:20 H: THE BECOOL PROJECT ON ADVANCED LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOFUELS

17th of December 2020: Value Chain Event on Lignocellulosic Crops – Opportunities for the agriculture sector

2nd on-line value chain event (20/1/21)

The 2nd on-line value chain event was co-organised with PANACEA project and was supported by four research projects namely ADAPT, UNTWIST, 4CE-MED & MEDIOPUNTIA. The agenda of this event is presented below.

Value Chain Event on Carbohydrate and Specialty Industrial Crops
Opportunities for the agriculture sector

20th of January 2021

13:50	Get connected	
14:00	Welcome	
	<i>Set the scene of the today workshop & presentation of PANACEA platform and MAGIC tools</i>	Dr. Efi Alexopoulou (CRES) Mr. Panayiotis Stamatelopoulos (AUA)
14:20	The ADAPT project: Using molecular understanding of stress acclimation to develop stress tolerant potatoes	Dr. Markus Teige (University of Vienna)
14:35	UNTWIST – Uncover and promote tolerance and water stress in camelina sativa	Dr. Claudia Jonak (Austrian Institute of Technology)
14:50	The Medi Opuntia project – Promoting cactus plantation on large scale in marginal lands of Mediterranean countries	Prof. Ana Luisa Fernando (FCT UNL)
15:10	Towards innovative medicinal plant value chains (Results of EIP-AGRI Focus Group 35)	Prof. Dimitrios Argyopoulos (UCD)
15:40	Sustainable Industrial Crops (Focus group 40): The situation of specialty crops	Dr. Juliana Navarro Rocha (CITA)
16:10	<i>Discussion on the value-chain of carbohydrate and specialty industrial crops</i>	
16:45	End of the webinar	

Supported by the projects

The event, focused on Carbohydrate and Specialty Crops and the opportunities for the agriculture sector. The starting point was PANACEA platform and which kind of information the practitioners can find on it (which projects, information on the crops, actions and activities of PANACEA on those crops). Selected on-going projects had been presented as good examples. More specifically, the ADAPT project (Accelerated Development of multiple-stress tolerant Potato) presented the current research of potato in Europe under combined environmental stress conditions. The UNTWIST project (Uncover and promote tolerance and water stress in camelina sativa) is a new project on camelina with emphasis on water stress.

It should be pointed out that camelina is a valuable cover/catch oilseed crop that is being promoted for the marginal lands of Europe that allow the farmers to have double cropping on the same year. Cactus is promoted by MEDIOPUNTIA project (Promoting cactus plantation on large scale in marginal lands of Mediterranean countries) for the dry areas around Med that having too many industrial applications and thus considering as multi-purpose crop. On the very same event it was presented the main finding of two focus groups; the first was on medicinal plants (<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/focus-groups/diversification-opportunities-through-plant-based>) and the second on industrial crops (<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/focus-groups/sustainable-industrial-crops-europe-new-market>). All the information for these two focus groups is available on eip agri website under focus groups.

Photos from this event are presented below.

Below is presented the dissemination of the event through social media.

It should be pointed out that in both events more than 100 people had been registered but the actual number of persons attended the events varied from 60 to 80. Moreover, it should be stressed out that it was difficult to do a long-lasting discussion with the participants in this kind on-line events and the audience can not stay there for more than 3 hours.